

ISic3140

I.Sicily inscription 3140

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Vigna Cassia

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329952

1. πρὸ ις' καλανδῶν
2. Ἀπριλίω[ν] ἔτελεύ-
3. τησεν καλώνυ-
4. μος Ἐλευθερίων
5. ἑτέων ἕξ.
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645481

PHI 329952

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 18.0401

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1960.0461

Agnello, S.L. 1956. Scavi recenti nelle catacombe di Vigna Cassia a Siracusa. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 32: 7-27. At 23a ph

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3140. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388207>